

1 **MELATONIN AUGMENTS THE NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECTS OF HYPOTHERMIA IN**
2 **LAMBS FOLLOWING PERINATAL ASPHYXIA**

3

4 James DS Aridas¹, Tamara Yawno^{1,2}, Amy E Sutherland¹, Ilias Nitsos^{1,2}, Flora Y Wong^{1,3,4}, Rod W
5 Hunt^{3,4,6}, Michael Ditchfield⁴, Michael C Fahey^{1,4,5}, Atul Malhotra^{1,3,4,5}, Euan M Wallace^{1,2}, Alistair J
6 Gunn⁷, Graham Jenkin^{1,2}, Suzanne L Miller^{1,2}.

7

8 ¹The Ritchie Centre, Hudson Institute of Medical Research, Clayton, Victoria, Australia

9 ²Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Monash University, Clayton, Victoria, Australia

10 ³Department of Paediatrics, Monash University, Clayton, Victoria, Australia

11 ⁴Monash Children's Hospital, Monash Health, Clayton, Victoria, Australia

12 ⁵Department of Paediatrics, Monash University, Clayton, Victoria, Australia

13 ⁶Murdoch Children's Research Institute, Melbourne, Victoria, Australia

14 ⁷Department of Physiology, School of Medical Sciences, University of Auckland, Auckland, New
15 Zealand

16

17 **Corresponding author:** Suzanne Miller, Ph.D., The Ritchie Centre, Hudson Institute of Medical
18 Research, 27-31 Wright Street, Clayton, VIC 3168, Australia.

19 e-mail: suzie.miller@monash.edu

20

21 **Conflict of interest statement:** The authors have declared that no conflict of interest exists.

22 **Keywords:** Perinatal asphyxia, therapeutic hypothermia, neonatal encephalopathy, neuroprotection,
23 melatonin, oxidative stress, brain injury.

24 **Data availability:** The data that support the findings of this study are available from the
25 corresponding author upon reasonable request.

26

27

28 **ABSTRACT**

29 Therapeutic hypothermia (TH) is standard care in high resource birth settings for infants with neonatal
30 encephalopathy. TH is partially effective and adjuvant therapies are needed. Here we examined
31 whether the antioxidant melatonin (MLT) provides additive benefit with TH, compared to TH alone or
32 MLT alone, to improve recovery from acute encephalopathy in newborn lambs. Immediately before
33 caesarean section delivery, we induced asphyxia in fetal sheep via umbilical cord occlusion until mean
34 arterial blood pressure fell from 55 ± 3 mmHg in sham controls to 18-20 mmHg (10.1±1.5 min).
35 Lambs were delivered and randomized to control, control+MLT (60mg i.v., from 30 min to 24 h),
36 asphyxia, asphyxia+TH (whole-body cooling to $35.1 \pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$ vs $38.3 \pm 0.17^\circ\text{C}$ in sham controls, from 4-
37 28 h), asphyxia+MLT, and asphyxia+TH+MLT. At 72 h, magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS)
38 was undertaken and then brains collected for neuropathology assessment. Asphyxia induced abnormal
39 brain metabolism on MRS with increased Lactate:NAA ($p=0.003$) and reduced NAA:Choline
40 ($p=0.005$), induced apoptotic and necrotic cell death across grey and white matter brain regions
41 ($p<0.05$), and increased neuroinflammation and oxidative stress ($p<0.05$). TH and MLT were
42 independently associated with region-specific reductions in oxidative stress, inflammation, and cell
43 death, compared to asphyxia alone. There was an interaction between TH and MLT such that the
44 NAA:Choline ratio was not significantly different after asphyxia+TH+MLT compared to sham
45 controls. but had a greater overall reduction in neuropathology than either treatment alone. This study
46 demonstrates that, in newborn lambs, combined TH+MLT for neonatal encephalopathy provides
47 significantly greater neuroprotection than either alone. These results will guide development of further
48 trials for neonatal encephalopathy.

49

50

51 INTRODUCTION

52 Neonatal encephalopathy describes acute, evolving abnormal neurological function in the days after
53 birth. The etiology of neonatal encephalopathy is most commonly severe acute hypoxic-ischemic or
54 asphyxic episode around the time of birth but may also involve other factors and hence the move away
55 from the older term, hypoxic-ischaemic encephalopathy (HIE)¹. In all birth settings, neonatal
56 encephalopathy is a primary cause for premature death or long-term disability. Therapeutic
57 hypothermia (TH) is standard care for term infants with moderate to severe neonatal encephalopathy
58 in high income countries². Reducing infant body temperature by 3.5 ± 0.5 °C (i.e. to 33.5–34.5°C),
59 commencing within 6 hours of birth and continuing for 72 hours, reduces mortality and moderate-to-
60 severe neurodevelopmental disability at 18 months of age^{2,4}. Nevertheless, benefits of TH for infants
61 with neonatal encephalopathy are only partial, and in the original randomized controlled trials, nearly
62 half of encephalopathic newborns treated with TH died, or survived with disabilities⁴. Improved
63 outcomes for infants with neonatal encephalopathy require adjuvant approaches to augment
64 hypothermic neuroprotection.

65 Melatonin (MLT) is a candidate neuroprotective treatment due to its potent antioxidant properties.
66 MLT is safe in pregnancy and in the neonate and readily crosses the blood-brain barrier⁵⁻⁹. In
67 preclinical fetal sheep studies, MLT attenuates brain hydroxyl radical production following hypoxia-
68 ischemia and reduces markers of circulating oxidative stress, improves functional recovery of brain
69 activity, and reduces brain inflammation and cell death^{5,6,10}. Following asphyxia at birth in lambs,
70 MLT is an effective stand-alone neuroprotective therapy, preventing brain metabolic dysfunction on
71 magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) and reducing neuropathology¹¹. In a piglet model of neonatal
72 encephalopathy after hypoxia-ischemia, the Robertson group were the first to demonstrate that MLT
73 combined with TH significantly improved MRS-indices of brain metabolism and reduced cell
74 death^{12,13}. There are no studies to date in which TH alone, MLT alone, and TH+MLT have been
75 assessed head-to-head, to directly compare the separate and additive effects of these therapies on
76 neuropathology and functional outcomes subsequent to perinatal asphyxia.

77 Our aim in the current study was to examine in lambs whether MLT enhanced the neuroprotective
78 benefits of TH following asphyxia at birth, compared to either TH alone or MLT alone. We tested the
79 hypothesis that MLT would provide additive neuroprotective benefit to TH following asphyxia at
80 birth, and that TH+MLT together would provide greater neuroprotection than either treatment alone,
81 using our well characterized near-term lamb model of asphyxia at birth.^{11,14,15} This study included a
82 total of 6 cohorts of lambs: control, control+MLT, asphyxia, asphyxia+MLT, asphyxia+TH,
83 asphyxia+TH+MLT, in order to assess the separate effects of TH and MLT, plus their combined
84 actions.

85

86 **MATERIALS & METHODS**

87 Experiments were undertaken following the Australian NHMRC code for the care and use of animals
88 for scientific purposes and had institutional approval. Animals were sourced from the Monash Animal
89 Research Platform.

90 **Surgery**

91 Pregnant ewes at 139–141 days gestation (term is ~145d) under general anesthesia underwent surgery
92 induced by sodium-thiopentone (20mg/kg IV; Pentothal, Boehringer Ingelheim, Australia) and
93 maintained with 1–2.5% isoflurane (IsoFlo, Abott Laboratories, USA) in oxygen/nitrous oxide (O₂: 2–
94 L; N₂O: 1L). With the lower limbs of the lamb exposed from the uterus, femoral artery and vein
95 catheters were inserted. Arterial blood samples were collected before asphyxia, at 8min during
96 occlusion, then at 4, 12, 24, 48 and 72h post asphyxia and delivery.

97 **Asphyxia and resuscitation**

98 Asphyxia was induced in fetal lambs by complete cord occlusion^{11,14,15} until arterial blood pressure fell
99 to 18-20mmHg, compared to 55 ± 3mmHg in sham controls. Lambs were delivered and resuscitated
100 with endotracheal intubation and positive pressure ventilation (NeoPuff, Fisher and Paykel Healthcare,
101 Australia; 30cm H₂O PIP; 5-8cm PEEP; 10L/min room air; 30breaths/min), and then ventilated

102 (Babylog 8000+, Dräger, Australia; volume guarantee 5mL/kg) until the lamb commenced
103 spontaneous breathing >50% of the time, after which ventilation was ceased.

104

105 **Neuroprotection strategies**

106 **Hypothermia**

107 Whole body TH to $35\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ was undertaken for 24h on asphyxia, asphyxia+TH and
108 asphyxia+TH+MLT lambs. This represented a target reduction of 3.5°C below normal temperature of
109 $\sim 38.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the lamb. At 3.5 h after birth, the lamb's belly was shaved, and a rectal temperature probe
110 (ADI Instruments, Australia) was placed. At 4h after birth, TH was induced using crushed ice within
111 large zip lock bags around the conscious lamb. Following 24h of TH (Table 1), the lamb was
112 rewarmed $0.5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{h}$ over a 10h period to $\sim 39^{\circ}\text{C}$.

113 **Melatonin**

114 MLT (Sigma-Aldrich, Australia) was administered IV to control+MLT, asphyxia+MLT and
115 asphyxia+TH+MLT lambs. MLT was prepared in absolute ethanol (5% final volume) and saline as
116 described previously¹¹ and administered via the femoral vein in 5mg boluses, starting 30min post
117 birth, and then every 2h until 24.5h, for a total dose of 60mg over 24h. We have previously shown this
118 dosing regimen to provide a sustained increase in circulating and brain melatonin that represents a
119 neuroprotective dose¹¹.

120 **Maintenance**

121 Blood sampling was used for clinical management (e.g. glucose and bicarbonate) and sheep milk
122 formula (Wombaroo, Glen Osmond, South Australia, Australia) was provided once lambs had attained
123 good suckling reflex. Until that time lambs were given maintenance fluids (10% glucose, 40ml/kg/d).

124 **Behavioral milestones**

125 Signs of encephalopathy were characterized using a modified Sarnat system¹⁴⁻¹⁶, including ability to
126 stand and feed, and seizure-like activity. Evidence of clinical seizures (jerking, spasms, stiffening of

127 limbs)¹⁷ required treatment with 20mg/kg phenobarbitone, administered IV over 30 min. Percentage of
128 time spent asleep over the first 24h was noted.

129 **Magnetic resonance spectroscopy**

130 At 72h, lambs were lightly sedated (medetomidine hydrochloride 0.1mg/kg, Domitor, Pfizer,
131 Australia) and MRI/MRS undertaken using a 3T Siemens Vario (Siemens Medical Solutions, PA,
132 USA) with an 8-channel knee coil (400x420x310 mm). MRS was performed using a 270 ms echo
133 time, 2cm³ voxel placed over deep grey matter containing hippocampus, striatum and basal ganglia for
134 assessment of choline (cho), n-acetyl aspartate (NAA), and lactate (lac) with computer generated area
135 under the curve analysis, and ratios were determined.

136 **Biological fluid markers of neuropathology**

137 MLT concentrations in plasma (fetal levels pre asphyxia, and 4h, 12h, 24h and 48h) and cerebral
138 cortex of the brain were assessed by radioimmunoassay kit as per manufacturer's instructions
139 (Buhlmann Laboratories, Schonenbuch, Switzerland) with a sensitivity of 0.3pg/ml, intra-assay
140 precision of 7.9% and inter-assay precision of 11.7%. Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) was collected at post
141 mortem and concentrations of malondialdehyde (MDA) measured using a thiobarbituric acid reactive
142 substances (TBARS) assay⁹ (assay sensitivity of 0.1µmol/L, intra-assay precision 3.1% and inter-
143 assay precision 5.1%), S100 calcium binding protein B (S100B), (DiaSorin, Stillwater, USA; assay
144 sensitivity 0.03µg/L, intra-assay precision <10%, inter-assay precision <15%) and cytokines (IL-1β,
145 IL-6, IL-10, and TNF-α) were also measured (Cytokine Bead Array, BD Biosciences, North Ryde,
146 Australia; >85% recovery of standards, sensitivity of 0.274pg/ml, intra-assay precision for IL-1β
147 157%, IL-6 164%, IL-10 120%, TNF-α 116%).

148 **Neurohistopathology**

149 At 72h, after the MRS measurements, lambs were killed (5mL pentobarbitone; 400mg/kg, Lethabarb,
150 Virac, Australia), and brains removed and weighed. The right brain hemisphere was cut into 5mm
151 slices coronally and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde for 48h, followed by paraffin embedding and
152 coronal section at 10µm. Brain regions were analyzed at the perirolandic cortex, including

153 hippocampus (CA1), cortex (molecular layer), thalamus (paraventricular nuclei), striatum (external
154 capsule), and subcortical white matter. Immunohistochemistry was carried out as previously
155 described^{11,14,15} with lipid peroxidation analyzed using 4-hydroxynonenal (4-HNE; 1:500; Millipore,
156 USA), all IBA-1-positive microglia and macrophages assessed using ionized calcium-binding adapter
157 molecule (IBA-1; 1:500; Wako Pure, Osaka, Japan), apoptotic cell death assessed using activated
158 caspase-3 (Cas-3; 1:1000, R&D Systems, MN, USA), and necrosis assessed via cresyl violet-acid
159 fuchsin (Amber Scientific, Midvale WA, Australia) staining to identify organelle swelling, pyknotic
160 nuclei, eosinophilic cytoplasm, or cells with condensed cytoplasm^{18,19}. The average number or percent
161 area coverage of positively stained cells across three fields of view were calculated using ImageJ
162 (v1.48, NIH).

163 **Statistical analyses**

164 Data are mean \pm SEM, with significance accepted when $p < 0.05$. Analysis was undertaken using
165 GraphPad Prism 8 (GraphPad Software, USA). A two-step analysis was performed, firstly examining
166 asphyxia versus control (control, asphyxia, control+MLT) via 1-way ANOVA, followed by 2-way
167 ANOVA with TH and MLT as independent variables to assess outcomes within the asphyxia groups
168 (asphyxia, asphyxia+TH, asphyxia+MLT, asphyxia+TH+MLT). Repeated measures analysis was
169 included for continuous data. Where a significant effect of the independent variables was found, post
170 hoc comparisons were made using Tukey's multiple comparisons for normally distributed data. Non-
171 parametric data were analyzed using Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA on ranks, with Dunn's method.

172

173 **RESULTS**

174 **Asphyxia and resuscitation**

175 Baseline group characteristics are shown in Table 1. Blood gas and physiological parameters were not
176 different between groups before asphyxia. Asphyxia induced severe metabolic acidosis in all groups
177 consistent with the clinical criteria for a severe acute hypoxic event at birth, $pH < 7$ and base excess $< -$
178 12^{20} ; pH in the asphyxia and asphyxia+TH+MLT groups was significantly different ($p = 0.044$), but

179 other parameters including duration of insult, and nadir of blood pressure and heart rate, and fetal
180 oxygen saturation were not different between the asphyxia groups.

181 **Hypothermia**

182 TH lambs reached target temperature of 35°C within ~2.5h, and remained within 35±0.5°C circa 70%
183 of the time, Table 1. TH lambs were rewarmed over 10h, and then remained stable at a core
184 temperature of > 38.5°C over the remaining experimental period.

185

186 **Melatonin**

187 MLT concentration was assessed during the experimental period in plasma, and in cortical brain tissue
188 after post mortem at 72 h, Figure 1A & B. MLT concentration was not different between groups prior
189 to asphyxia or MLT administration. As expected, iv. MLT administration significantly increased MLT
190 concentration; in the control+MLT group, from baseline plasma MLT 0.08 ± 0.04 ng/ml to 425 ± 172
191 ng/ml at 12 h (p<0.001). Interestingly, circulating MLT concentrations were greater in the
192 asphyxia+TH+MLT group than in the control+MLT and asphyxia+MLT groups (p<0.001). This
193 difference was most notable at 48 h, when circulating levels were returning to baseline in both
194 control+MLT and asphyxia+MLT cohorts (p<0.01, 24 h vs. 48 h) whereas the asphyxia+TH+MLT
195 lambs showed no decrease in MLT concentrations from 24 h to 48 h (p=0.79). Brain concentrations of
196 MLT were significantly elevated at 72 h in MLT-treated animals compared to asphyxia alone, but
197 were not different in the asphyxia+TH+MLT and asphyxia+MLT groups (p=0.68).

198 **Maintenance**

199 By 4h after birth, all animals demonstrated stable physiological parameters (heart rate, SaO₂, base
200 excess and lactate), Table 1. At 12h, asphyxia lambs showed secondary increase in base excess
201 (p=0.01) and lactate (p=0.01) compared to control. Within the asphyxia groups, 2-way ANOVA
202 showed that TH prevented the secondary increase in lactate (p=0.002 at 24h), but MLT did not
203 (p=0.95), and there was no interaction between interventions (p=0.08).

204 **Behavioral milestones**

205 Control+MLT lambs showed behavioral outcomes expected for normal lambs but spent more time
206 sleeping over the first 24h (control: 37%; control+MLT 63%; $p=0.04$), Table 2. Time to establish
207 spontaneous feeding was delayed in asphyxia compared to the control groups ($p=0.002$). MLT
208 treatment reduced the time taken for lambs to feed ($p<0.001$), whereas TH increased the time taken to
209 feed ($p=0.004$), and there was no significant interaction between the treatments ($p=0.06$). At 72h, all
210 control lambs could stand unaided. 11/16 asphyxia lambs could stand, but they took ~9-times longer
211 than control lambs to attain standing position ($p<0.0001$). TH further increased the time to stand
212 ($p=0.001$, asphyxia vs asphyxia+TH). Overt clinical seizures were present in 7/16 asphyxia lambs (vs
213 0/15 control, $p=0.04$). MLT treatment was associated with decreased seizures ($p=0.03$ vs asphyxia)
214 but TH was not ($p=0.16$), with no interaction.

215 **Magnetic resonance spectroscopy**

216 Asphyxia alone was associated with a >2-fold increase in Lactate:Choline ratio ($p=0.04$ vs controls), a
217 decrease in NAA:Choline ($p=0.005$), and 4-fold increase in Lactate:NAA ($p=0.003$), Figure 2. Two-
218 way ANOVA in the asphyxia groups showed that Lactate:Choline ratio was not significantly altered
219 by MLT ($p=0.13$) or TH ($p=0.49$) and there was no interaction between variables ($p=0.38$).

220 NAA:Choline after asphyxia was not altered by MLT ($p=0.11$) or TH ($p=0.13$) but there was an
221 interaction between TH and MLT ($p=0.03$), such that the asphyxia+TH+MLT group was not
222 significantly different from controls. Lactate:NAA ratio after asphyxia was significantly reduced with
223 MLT ($p=0.008$) but not TH ($p=0.57$), with no interaction ($p=0.36$). The asphyxia+TH+MLT lambs
224 had metabolite concentrations that were not significantly different from control levels for all cerebral
225 metabolic outcomes.

226 **Oxidative stress**

227 Cerebral oxidative stress was measured as MDA in CSF at post mortem (Figure 3A) and 4-HNE in
228 brain tissue, Figure 3B, 6A-E. MDA was elevated 3-fold in CSF from asphyxia lambs versus control
229 ($p=0.02$). Both MLT ($p<0.0001$) and hypothermia ($p=0.0004$) were associated with reduced MDA in

230 CSF, with no interaction ($p=0.45$) and the combined treatment group asphyxia+TH+MLT was
231 significantly reduced compared to asphyxia alone ($p<0.0001$) and asphyxia+TH ($p=0.03$). 4-HNE cell
232 counts were not affected by asphyxia, but MLT significantly reduced 4-HNE cells within the thalamus
233 only ($p=0.006$; Figure 3B), and TH had no effect.

234 **Inflammation**

235 IL-1 β was the only cytokine that showed an appreciable increase within the CSF at 72h after asphyxia
236 in asphyxia alone animals, Figure 4A. This increase in IL-1 β was not present in any of the treatment
237 groups. Neuroinflammation was assessed via IBA-1 cell counts, Figure 4B, 6F-J. Asphyxia increased
238 IBA-1+ microglia within the cortex, hippocampus, striatum and white matter ($p<0.05$ vs control).
239 Across the asphyxia groups, TH significantly reduced IBA-1 cell counts within all grey matter brain
240 regions ($p<0.01$, 2-way ANOVA), with no significant effect in white matter. Similarly, MLT reduced
241 IBA-1 in all brain regions ($p<0.05$), but with no significant effect in the striatum. There was no
242 interaction between treatments for any brain region.

243 **Cell death**

244 S100B is a marker of neuronal and astrocyte damage. S100B levels were increased in CSF >5-fold
245 following asphyxia ($p=0.002$ vs control, Figure 5A). Within the asphyxia groups, MLT treatment
246 decreased S100B ($p<0.0001$), but TH did not ($p=0.46$). Post-hoc analysis suggested that both the
247 asphyxia+MLT and asphyxia+TH+MLT groups showed a significant decrease in S100B compared to
248 asphyxia alone. No treatment interaction was present ($p=0.1$).

249 Degenerating neurons stained with cresyl violet-acid fuchsin and morphological evidence of necrosis
250 were counted (Figure 5B, 6K-O). Asphyxia alone was associated with a >2-fold increase in necrotic
251 cell counts ($p<0.001$ for all regions vs control). Within the asphyxia groups, 2-way ANOVA showed
252 that TH was associated with a reduction in neuronal necrosis within the hippocampus, thalamus and
253 striatum ($p<0.05$) and MLT reduced necrosis across all brain regions ($p<0.001$), with no significant
254 interaction. On post-hoc analysis, neuronal necrosis was reduced in the asphyxia+TH group compared
255 to asphyxia in the hippocampus only ($p<0.05$), while asphyxia+MLT was different to asphyxia across

256 all brain regions ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, post-hoc analysis showed that neuronal degeneration was
257 reduced to a greater degree in the asphyxia+TH+MLT group than asphyxia+TH within hippocampus,
258 thalamus and striatum ($p < 0.05$; Figure 5B).

259 Apoptosis was assessed using activated caspase-3 immunoreactivity and quantified as % area stained
260 (Figure 5C, Figure 6P-T). A significant increase in activated caspase-3-area was observed in all brain
261 regions after asphyxia (Figure 5C, 6P-T). Within the asphyxia groups, 2-way ANOVA showed that
262 TH reduced activated caspase-3-area in all brain regions ($p \leq 0.0001$ for cortex, thalamus, striatum and
263 white matter, and $p = 0.002$ for hippocampus), while MLT treatment was associated with a significant
264 reduction in activated caspase-3-area across all brain regions ($p < 0.05$), except the cortex ($p = 0.065$).
265 MLT augmented the anti-apoptotic effects of TH within the thalamus and striatum, as shown by a
266 significant treatment interaction ($p < 0.05$). On post-hoc analysis, activated caspase-3-area was reduced
267 in each of the asphyxia+TH, asphyxia+MLT and asphyxia+TH+MLT groups compared to asphyxia
268 alone.

269

270 **DISCUSSION**

271 This study used a translational approach in lambs to demonstrate that TH and melatonin independently
272 mediate neuroprotection after asphyxia and delivery by cesarean section. The addition of melatonin to
273 therapeutic hypothermia additively augmented neuroprotection, with independent effects of TH and
274 MLT to reduced inflammation, oxidative stress and both necrotic and apoptotic cell death. The
275 combination of MLT i.v., commenced 30 minutes after asphyxia at birth, together with whole body
276 TH started at 4 hours, improved neuro-behavioral outcomes, improved brain metabolic and
277 biochemical profiles and reduced cell death. Results of this study confirm previous evidence that early
278 initiation of MLT treatment is neuroprotective for perinatal asphyxia¹¹ and that MLT augments
279 hypothermic neuroprotection^{12,13,21-23}. Here we extend these findings to show that the benefits of
280 combined TH with MLT following birth asphyxia in lambs are greater than when either treatment is
281 used in isolation across multiple indices of brain structure and function, including clinical markers of
282 cerebral metabolism on MRS, and for caspase-3-mediated apoptosis.

283 Therapeutic hypothermia is the gold standard for treatment of neonatal encephalopathy, based on
284 preclinical and clinical evidence that cooling reduces the progression of neuropathology and improves
285 functional outcomes^{2,24,25}. In the present study, TH was commenced at 4 hours after birth asphyxia in
286 lambs using ice packs, as per the ICE trial²⁶, and lambs were cooled for 24 hours to 35°C to reduce
287 temperature by $\sim 3.5 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ compared to sham control lambs. We continued TH for 24 hours to align
288 with evidence in piglets that this is feasible and neuroprotective²⁷. Our results confirm that whole body
289 cooling by 3.5°C for 24 hours independently prevents a secondary increase in circulating lactate,
290 neuroinflammation and cerebral apoptosis, with a brain-region specific reduction in necrotic cell
291 death, consistent with previous preclinical experimental studies²⁸⁻³⁰. By contrast, in the present study
292 TH did not improve the lactate:NAA ratio on MRS, whereas previous clinical assessment supports that
293 TH improves this measure³¹. We acknowledge that this could reflect that the duration of TH was not
294 sufficient for maximal neuroprotection in the current study, where 72 hours of TH in fetal sheep
295 consistently provides optimal effect³². Nevertheless, TH provided independent neuroprotection across
296 multiple outcome measures, confirming that this protocol provides a robust basis to test adjuvant
297 therapies to augment neuroprotection with TH after perinatal asphyxia.

298 MLT infusion resulted in a rapid and sustained increase in circulating MLT levels, and brain
299 concentrations of MLT at 72h (48h after the final MLT administration) were elevated in MLT groups.
300 Interestingly, circulating MLT levels remained elevated in asphyxia+TH+MLT lambs compared to the
301 asphyxia+MLT group. This may reflect suppression of basal metabolic rate and drug clearance by
302 TH³³, reducing liver metabolism and renal excretion of MLT. This prolonged elevation in circulating
303 MLT may have contributed to the greater neuroprotection seen in the asphyxia+TH+MLT group
304 compared to other treatment groups, although brain MLT levels at 72 hours were not different across
305 MLT treated groups. We have previously shown that even a smaller increase in cerebral MLT is
306 neuroprotective¹¹. MLT administration was associated with independent neuroprotective effects,
307 including reduced cerebral lipid peroxidation production and, at least regionally, decreased oxidative
308 stress within the thalamus³⁴. MLT was also associated with anti-inflammatory and anti-apoptotic
309 effects across many brain regions, and reduced neuronal degeneration across all brain regions. A

310 number of these effects of MLT were similar to actions of TH, but interestingly, MLT but not TH was
311 associated with reduced cerebral Lactate:NAA at 72h and MLT reduced the cerebral injury marker
312 S100B in CSF whereas TH did not.

313 In this study we utilized a modified Sarnat grading system to assess neonatal lamb wellbeing and time
314 to achieve typical milestones that consider feeding ability, standing unaided and physical presence of
315 seizures-like activity^{15,16}. As expected, asphyxia lambs showed abnormalities in all of these
316 milestones. The results show that 100% of asphyxia+TH+MLT animals were able to stand
317 independently and feed from a bottle at 72 hours, and the time taken to achieve feeding and standing
318 were significantly reduced compared to TH alone. Furthermore, it is notable that none of the lambs in
319 the asphyxia+TH+MLT group exhibited physical signs of seizure-like activity, compared to 44% in
320 the asphyxia alone group, suggesting that MLT augments the effects of TH to prevent seizures. Many
321 neonatal seizures in NE are clinically silent, and so this result requires confirmation with EEG
322 monitoring. Thus, co-treatment of MLT with TH improved neurological recovery compared to both
323 asphyxia alone and asphyxia+TH. These marked improvements in functional outcomes are an
324 excellent sign for clinical applicability.

325 Increased Lactate:NAA and/or a decrease in NAA (either NAA:Choline or NAA:Creatine) in the
326 neonatal period following perinatal asphyxia are highly predictive for death or major disability at 12-
327 24 months^{35,36}. In the current study, Lactate:Choline, NAA:Choline and Lactate:NAA were all
328 significantly affected at 72h after asphyxia (Figure 2), demonstrating cerebral metabolic disturbance
329 and reduced neuronal wellbeing³⁷. Following asphyxia, MLT treatment but not TH was independently
330 associated with improved Lactate:NAA ratio. It was interesting that neither TH or MLT independently
331 improved NAA:Choline, but that combination treatment was associated with a significant interaction
332 effect, such that NAA:Choline values in the asphyxia+TH+MLT animals were improved and not
333 different from controls. Our data reveal a discrepancy between the lack of change in NAA:Choline as
334 a measure of neuronal function in the deep gray matter of asphyxia+MLT and asphyxia+TH groups,
335 compared with reduced histological cellular necrosis and apoptosis in these groups. A reduction in
336 brain NAA is considered a sensitive marker for reduced neuronal metabolism, but there remains

337 conjecture regarding whether this is reversible or irreversible³⁸. Our results suggest that both MLT and
338 TH independently reduced neuronal necrosis and apoptosis, but that these cell populations may not be
339 fully functional at 72 hours. Critically, for both the MRS measure of NAA:Choline and apoptotic
340 assessment of cell death our results strongly support the concept that MLT augments the
341 neuroprotective action of TH to maintain neuronal wellbeing following severe asphyxia.

342 Neuronal loss following a severe perinatal asphyxic insult is mediated via both apoptotic and necrotic
343 cell degeneration¹⁹. MLT exhibited strong neuroprotective benefit to reduce necrosis across all brain
344 regions, while TH reduced neuronal necrosis only in the deep grey matter brain regions of the
345 thalamus, striatum and hippocampus. Conversely, TH was strongly anti-apoptotic across all brain
346 regions, whereas the effects of MLT were region-specific. These observations support previous work
347 in newborn infants that TH has a greater effect to suppress apoptotic cell death versus necrotic cell
348 death^{39,40} and suggests that MLT prevents necrosis to a greater extent than apoptosis. Neuronal death
349 following severe asphyxia is a continuum and caspase-3-dependent apoptosis persists from days to
350 weeks to mediate neonatal encephalopathy⁴¹. An interaction was observed between TH and MLT for
351 anti-apoptotic benefit within the deep grey matter of the thalamus and striatum (Figure 5B), indicating
352 that MLT augments TH to reduce apoptosis to a greater degree than either treatment alone.

353 Perinatal asphyxia initiates profound cerebral oxidative stress and inflammatory responses, which are
354 critical mediators of neuronal degeneration⁴². MLT and TH can both prevent mitochondrial
355 dysfunction^{43,44}, and MLT is a potent direct scavenger of ROS⁴⁵. Therefore it is not surprising that in
356 the current study we show that cerebral lipid peroxidation products (MDA in CSF and cellular 4-HNE)
357 were reduced in the asphyxia+MLT and asphyxia+TH lambs compared to asphyxia alone, albeit
358 antioxidant effects for both TH and MLT were partial and region-specific (Figure 3). Strikingly, we
359 show that the combination of MLT and TH has substantial antioxidant benefits in response to
360 asphyxia, with the lipid peroxide product MDA significantly reduced in the asphyxia+TH+MLT group
361 compared to asphyxia+TH. The combined treatment group had the lowest levels of cellular lipid
362 peroxidation across all groups and brain regions. Similarly, the present study confirms that TH and
363 MLT independently reduce cellular neuroinflammation^{6,46,47}. The present study supports independent

364 actions of TH and MLT, with no interactions between the two interventions, but that the effects of the
365 combined treatments were generally broader and more pronounced; for example, only the
366 asphyxia+TH+MLT group had reduced neuroinflammation compared to asphyxia alone in all grey
367 matter regions.

368 We aimed to use a clinically applicable model of perinatal asphyxia and neonatal care and monitoring;
369 however, some limitations should be considered. Firstly, it will be challenging to clinically administer
370 MLT within the first hour after birth and 2-hourly IV administration would be onerous during neonatal
371 intensive care. A continuous i.v. infusion may be possible. Alternatively, intragastric administration of
372 melatonin in preterm and term human infants^{48,49}, has been associated with sustained melatonin
373 concentrations with reduced frequency of administration compared to animal studies. We also found
374 that early administration of MLT made normal lambs sleepier than controls, and this sleepiness may
375 mask the encephalopathic symptoms that guide the requirement for TH. Finally, MLT was dissolved
376 in ethanol prior to intravenous administration. We did not include a control or asphyxia group with
377 vehicle (ethanol) only. Others have shown that ethanol itself may mediate brain-region specific
378 neuroprotection within the developing brain^{10,13}. We do however note that Robertson and colleagues¹³
379 are exploring an ethanol-free MLT formulation and this will be critical for the translation of this work.
380 It also should be noted that lambs in TH groups (asphyxia+TH and asphyxia+TH+MLT) spent ~70%
381 of time at the goal cooled temperature of $35\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$, and, combined with a reduced 24 hour period of
382 TH compared to the clinical situation would likely contribute to reduced efficacy of hypothermia
383 treatment. Our results support that both TH and MLT and combined treatments are safe. The only
384 potential adverse effects were a tachycardic response to TH at 12 h, and sedative effects of MLT and
385 TH. TH is now routine clinical care for neonatal encephalopathy⁵⁰. Although MLT is not used
386 routinely in neonatal care, it has been administered to newborns without adverse effects⁵¹.

387 This study supports that MLT has additive neuroprotective benefits when used together with TH for
388 neonatal encephalopathy. Importantly, TH and MLT together had significant additive benefits, such
389 that outcomes were better than when either TH or MLT was given in isolation. We observed a
390 significant interaction between TH and MLT to restore functional outcomes and normalization of

391 neuronal function (NAA) on MRS. Critically, 100% of asphyxia+TH+MLT lambs were able to stand
392 and feed, in contrast with only partial recovery in the TH and MLT groups. Although both TH and
393 MLT independently showed antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, there were no apparent
394 interactions between these outcomes, suggesting that other mechanisms contributed to the combined
395 benefits. Interestingly, the cellular effects of TH and MLT appear to be region-specific within the
396 brain, and, in co-treated group showed more consistent neuroprotection across multiple regions. A
397 significant treatment interaction within the deep gray matter for caspase-3-mediated apoptosis
398 indicates that MLT augments the neuroprotective benefits of TH to reduce ongoing cell death. These
399 findings confirm the neuroprotective efficacy of TH in a lamb model of perinatal asphyxia and
400 demonstrate that MLT provides additive neuroprotective benefit. These results will guide future trials
401 of combined treatments to improve outcomes for infants with neonatal encephalopathy.

402

403

404 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

405 The authors gratefully acknowledge the expert technical assistance of Jan Loose, Yen Pham, Courtney
406 McDonald, Domenic LaRosa, Stacey Ellery, Jingang Li, Madison Paton, Robert Alers, Lesley
407 Wiadrowski, David Shipp, Richard McIntyre, and Patricia Heidmann.

408

409 **FUNDING**

410 This study was supported by the National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) of
411 Australia, the Victorian Government's Operational Infrastructure Support Program, and the Bill and
412 Melinda Gates Foundation.

REFERENCES

- 1 Dammann O, Ferriero D & Gressens P 2011. Neonatal encephalopathy or hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy? Appropriate terminology matters. *Pediatr Res* 70(1);1-2.
- 2 Edwards AD, Brocklehurst P, Gunn AJ, Halliday H, Juszczak E, Levene M, Strohm B, Thoresen M, Whitelaw A & Azzopardi D 2010. Neurological outcomes at 18 months of age after moderate hypothermia for perinatal hypoxic ischaemic encephalopathy: synthesis and meta-analysis of trial data. *Bmj* 340;c363.
- 3 Azzopardi D, Strohm B, Marlow N, Brocklehurst P, Deierl A, Eddama O, Goodwin J, Halliday HL, Juszczak E, Kapellou O, Levene M, Linsell L, Omar O, Thoresen M, Tusor N, Whitelaw A, Edwards AD & Group TS 2014. Effects of hypothermia for perinatal asphyxia on childhood outcomes. *N Engl J Med* 371(2);140-149.
- 4 Jacobs SE, Berg M, Hunt R, Tarnow-Mordi WO, Inder TE & Davis PG 2013. Cooling for newborns with hypoxic ischaemic encephalopathy. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*(1);CD003311.
- 5 Miller SL, Yan EB, Castillo-Melendez M, Jenkin G & Walker DW 2005. Melatonin provides neuroprotection in the late-gestation fetal sheep brain in response to umbilical cord occlusion. *Dev Neurosci* 27(2-4);200-210.
- 6 Welin AK, Svedin P, Lapatto R, Sultan B, Hagberg H, Gressens P, Kjellmer I & Mallard C 2007. Melatonin reduces inflammation and cell death in white matter in the mid-gestation fetal sheep following umbilical cord occlusion. *Pediatr Res* 61(2);153-158.
- 7 Aversa S, Pellegrino S, Barberi I, Reiter RJ & Gitto E 2012. Potential utility of melatonin as an antioxidant during pregnancy and in the perinatal period. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med* 25(3);207-221.
- 8 Hobson SR, Lim R, Gardiner EE, Alers NO & Wallace EM 2013. Phase I pilot clinical trial of antenatal maternally administered melatonin to decrease the level of oxidative stress in human pregnancies affected by pre-eclampsia (PAMPR): study protocol. *BMJ Open* 3(9);e003788.
- 9 Miller SL, Yawno T, Alers NO, Castillo-Melendez M, Supramaniam VG, Vanzyl N, Sabaretnam T, Loose JM, Drummond GR, Walker DW, Jenkin G & Wallace EM 2014. Antenatal antioxidant treatment with melatonin to decrease newborn neurodevelopmental deficits and brain injury caused by fetal growth restriction. *J Pineal Res* 56(3);283-294.
- 10 Drury PP, Davidson JO, Bennet L, Booth LC, Tan S, Fraser M, van den Heuvel LG & Gunn AJ 2014. Partial neural protection with prophylactic low-dose melatonin after asphyxia in preterm fetal sheep. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab* 34(1);126-135.
- 11 Aridas JDS, Yawno T, Sutherland AE, Nitsos I, Ditchfield M, Wong FY, Hunt RW, Fahey MC, Malhotra A, Wallace EM, Jenkin G & Miller SL 2018. Systemic and transdermal melatonin administration prevents neuropathology in response to perinatal asphyxia in newborn lambs. *J Pineal Res* 64(4);e12479.

- 12 Robertson NJ, Faulkner S, Fleiss B, Bainbridge A, Andorka C, Price D, Powell E, Lecky-Thompson L, Thei L, Chandrasekaran M, Hristova M, Cady EB, Gressens P, Golay X & Raivich G 2013. Melatonin augments hypothermic neuroprotection in a perinatal asphyxia model. *Brain* 136(Pt 1);90-105.
- 13 Robertson NJ, Lingam I, Meehan C, Martinello KA, Avdic-Belltheus A, Stein L, Tachrount M, Price D, Sokolska M, Bainbridge A, Hristova M, Fleiss B, Kramer BW, Gressens P & Golay X 2020. High-Dose Melatonin and Ethanol Excipient Combined with Therapeutic Hypothermia in a Newborn Piglet Asphyxia Model. *Sci Rep* 10(1);3898.
- 14 Aridas JD, McDonald CA, Paton MC, Yawno T, Sutherland AE, Nitsos I, Pham Y, Ditchfield M, Fahey MC, Wong F, Malhotra A, Castillo-Melendez M, Bhakoo K, Wallace EM, Jenkin G & Miller SL 2016. Cord blood mononuclear cells prevent neuronal apoptosis in response to perinatal asphyxia in the newborn lamb. *J Physiol* 594(5);1421-1435.
- 15 Aridas JD, Yawno T, Sutherland AE, Nitsos I, Ditchfield M, Wong FY, Fahey MC, Malhotra A, Wallace EM, Jenkin G & Miller SL 2014. Detecting brain injury in neonatal hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy: closing the gap between experimental and clinical research. *Exp Neurol* 261;281-290.
- 16 Castillo-Melendez M, Baburamani AA, Cabalag C, Yawno T, Witjaksono A, Miller SL & Walker DW 2013. Experimental modelling of the consequences of brief late gestation asphyxia on newborn lamb behaviour and brain structure. *PLoS One* 8(11);e77377.
- 17 Nguyen T & Wusthoff CJ 2021. Clinical Manifestations of Neonatal Seizures. *Pediatr Int*.
- 18 Castillo-Melendez M, Chow JA & Walker DW 2004. Lipid peroxidation, caspase-3 immunoreactivity, and pyknosis in late-gestation fetal sheep brain after umbilical cord occlusion. *Pediatr Res* 55(5);864-871.
- 19 Northington FJ, Chavez-Valdez R & Martin LJ 2011. Neuronal cell death in neonatal hypoxia-ischemia. *Ann Neurol* 69(5);743-758.
- 20 MacLennan AH, Thompson SC & Gecz J 2015. Cerebral palsy: causes, pathways, and the role of genetic variants. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 213(6);779-788.
- 21 Ahmed J, Pullattayil SA, Robertson NJ & More K 2021. Melatonin for neuroprotection in neonatal encephalopathy: A systematic review & meta-analysis of clinical trials. *Eur J Paediatr Neurol* 31;38-45.
- 22 Pang R, Avdic-Belltheus A, Meehan C, Martinello K, Mutshiya T, Yang Q, Sokolska M, Torrealdea F, Hristova M, Bainbridge A, Golay X, Juul SE & Robertson NJ 2021. Melatonin and/or erythropoietin combined with hypothermia in a piglet model of perinatal asphyxia. *Brain Commun* 3(1);fcaa211.
- 23 Carloni S, Facchinetti F, Pelizzi N, Buonocore G & Balduini W 2018. Melatonin Acts in Synergy with Hypothermia to Reduce Oxygen-Glucose Deprivation-Induced Cell Death in Rat Hippocampus Organotypic Slice Cultures. *Neonatology* 114(4);364-371.

- 24 Shah PS 2010. Hypothermia: a systematic review and meta-analysis of clinical trials. *Semin Fetal Neonatal Med* 15(5);238-246.
- 25 Gunn AJ, Gunn TR, de Haan HH, Williams CE & Gluckman PD 1997. Dramatic neuronal rescue with prolonged selective head cooling after ischemia in fetal lambs. *J Clin Invest* 99(2);248-256.
- 26 Jacobs SE, Morley CJ, Inder TE, Stewart MJ, Smith KR, McNamara PJ, Wright IM, Kirpalani HM, Darlow BA & Doyle LW 2011. Whole-body hypothermia for term and near-term newborns with hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy: a randomized controlled trial. *Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med* 165(8);692-700.
- 27 O'Brien FE, Iwata O, Thornton JS, De Vita E, Sellwood MW, Iwata S, Sakata YS, Charman S, Ordidge R, Cady EB, Wyatt JS & Robertson NJ 2006. Delayed whole-body cooling to 33 or 35 degrees C and the development of impaired energy generation consequential to transient cerebral hypoxia-ischemia in the newborn piglet. *Pediatrics* 117(5);1549-1559.
- 28 Davidson JO, Draghi V, Whitham S, Dhillon SK, Wassink G, Bennet L & Gunn AJ 2018. How long is sufficient for optimal neuroprotection with cerebral cooling after ischemia in fetal sheep? *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab* 38(6);1047-1059.
- 29 Thoresen M, Bagenholm R, Loberg EM, Apricena F & Kjellmer I 1996. Posthypoxic cooling of neonatal rats provides protection against brain injury. *Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed* 74(1);F3-9.
- 30 Thoresen M, Penrice J, Lorek A, Cady EB, Wylezinska M, Kirkbride V, Cooper CE, Brown GC, Edwards AD, Wyatt JS & et al. 1995. Mild hypothermia after severe transient hypoxia-ischemia ameliorates delayed cerebral energy failure in the newborn piglet. *Pediatr Res* 37(5);667-670.
- 31 Bonifacio SL, Saporta A, Glass HC, Lee P, Glidden DV, Ferriero DM, Barkovich AJ & Xu D 2012. Therapeutic hypothermia for neonatal encephalopathy results in improved microstructure and metabolism in the deep gray nuclei. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 33(11);2050-2055.
- 32 Davies A, Wassink G, Bennet L, Gunn AJ & Davidson JO 2019. Can we further optimize therapeutic hypothermia for hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy? *Neural Regen Res* 14(10);1678-1683.
- 33 van den Broek MP, Groenendaal F, Egberts AC & Rademaker CM 2010. Effects of hypothermia on pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics: a systematic review of preclinical and clinical studies. *Clin Pharmacokinet* 49(5);277-294.
- 34 Galano A, Tan DX & Reiter RJ 2011. Melatonin as a natural ally against oxidative stress: a physicochemical examination. *J Pineal Res* 51(1);1-16.
- 35 Zou R, Xiong T, Zhang L, Li S, Zhao F, Tong Y, Qu Y & Mu D 2018. Proton Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy Biomarkers in Neonates With Hypoxic-Ischemic Encephalopathy: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Front Neurol* 9;732.

- 36 Cady EB 2001. Magnetic resonance spectroscopy in neonatal hypoxic-ischaemic insults. *Childs Nerv Syst* 17(3);145-149.
- 37 Azzopardi D & Edwards AD 2010. Magnetic resonance biomarkers of neuroprotective effects in infants with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy. *Semin Fetal Neonatal Med* 15(5);261-269.
- 38 Moffett JR, Ross B, Arun P, Madhavarao CN & Namboodiri AM 2007. N-Acetylaspartate in the CNS: from neurodiagnostics to neurobiology. *Prog Neurobiol* 81(2);89-131.
- 39 Wassink G, Gunn ER, Drury PP, Bennet L & Gunn AJ 2014. The mechanisms and treatment of asphyxial encephalopathy. *Front Neurosci* 8;40.
- 40 Edwards AD, Yue X, Squier MV, Thoresen M, Cady EB, Penrice J, Cooper CE, Wyatt JS, Reynolds EO & Mehmet H 1995. Specific inhibition of apoptosis after cerebral hypoxia-ischaemia by moderate post-insult hypothermia. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 217(3);1193-1199.
- 41 Nakajima W, Ishida A, Lange MS, Gabrielson KL, Wilson MA, Martin LJ, Blue ME & Johnston MV 2000. Apoptosis has a prolonged role in the neurodegeneration after hypoxic ischemia in the newborn rat. *J Neurosci* 20(21);7994-8004.
- 42 Ferriero DM 2004. Neonatal brain injury. *N Engl J Med* 351(19);1985-1995.
- 43 Fischer TW, Zmijewski MA, Wortsman J & Slominski A 2008. Melatonin maintains mitochondrial membrane potential and attenuates activation of initiator (casp-9) and effector caspases (casp-3/casp-7) and PARP in UVR-exposed HaCaT keratinocytes. *J Pineal Res* 44(4);397-407.
- 44 Huang CH, Chen HW, Tsai MS, Hsu CY, Peng RH, Wang TD, Chang WT & Chen WJ 2009. Antiapoptotic cardioprotective effect of hypothermia treatment against oxidative stress injuries. *Acad Emerg Med* 16(9);872-880.
- 45 Reiter RJ, Tan DX, Osuna C & Gitto E 2000. Actions of melatonin in the reduction of oxidative stress. A review. *J Biomed Sci* 7(6);444-458.
- 46 Yawno T, Castillo-Melendez M, Jenkin G, Wallace EM, Walker DW & Miller SL 2012. Mechanisms of melatonin induced protection in the brain of late gestation fetal sheep in response to hypoxia. *Dev Neurosci* 34;543-551.
- 47 Wassink G, Davidson JO, Fraser M, Yuill CA, Bennet L & Gunn AJ 2020. Non-additive effects of adjunct erythropoietin therapy with therapeutic hypothermia after global cerebral ischaemia in near-term fetal sheep. *J Physiol* 598(5);999-1015.
- 48 Balduini W, Weiss MD, Carloni S, Rocchi M, Sura L, Rossignol C, Longini M, Bazzini F, Perrone S, Ott D, Wadhawan R & Buonocore G 2019. Melatonin pharmacokinetics and dose extrapolation after enteral infusion in neonates subjected to hypothermia. *J Pineal Res* 66(4);e12565.
- 49 Carloni S, Proietti F, Rocchi M, Longini M, Marseglia L, D'Angelo G, Balduini W, Gitto E & Buonocore G 2017. Melatonin Pharmacokinetics Following Oral Administration in Preterm Neonates. *Molecules* 22(12).

- 50 Wassink G, Davidson JO, Lear CA, Juul SE, Northington F, Bennet L & Gunn AJ 2018. A working model for hypothermic neuroprotection. *J Physiol* 596(23);5641-5654.
- 51 Sanchez-Barcelo EJ, Mediavilla MD & Reiter RJ 2011. Clinical uses of melatonin in pediatrics. *Int J Pediatr* 2011;892624.

Table 1. Lamb physiological outcomes. Significantly different values indicated in bold. Data are mean \pm standard error of the mean. * $p < 0.05$ vs control; # $p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia; $\phi p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia+MLT.

	Control	Control+MLT	Asphyxia	Asphyxia+TH	Asphyxia+MLT	Asphyxia+TH+MLT
GROUP CHARACTERISTICS						
Number (Male/Female)	9 (5/4)	6 (1/5)	16 (6/10)	12 (6/6)	14 (8/6)	6 (3/3)
In-utero						
- Heart rate (bpm)	199 \pm 11	194 \pm 14	183 \pm 6	226 \pm 15	197 \pm 14	213 \pm 18
- SaO ₂ (%)	68.1 \pm 3.8	68.9 \pm 3.5	69.0 \pm 3.6	72.3 \pm 2.9	73.9 \pm 1.9	75.7 \pm 3.3
- pH	7.26 \pm 0.02	7.28 \pm 0.01	7.23 \pm 0.02	7.29 \pm 0.02	7.24 \pm 0.01	7.31 \pm 0.03
- Base excess (mmol/L)	-0.5 \pm 0.9	-0.1 \pm 0.6	-2.1 \pm 1.2	-2.0 \pm 0.8	-0.2 \pm 0.3	-0.9 \pm 0.9
- Lactate (mmol/L)	2.2 \pm 0.2	2.4 \pm 0.2	2.6 \pm 0.2	2.1 \pm 0.1	2.5 \pm 0.2	2.4 \pm 0.4
Asphyxia						
- UCO duration (min)	-	-	9.9 \pm 0.5	10.3 \pm 0.4	9.7 \pm 0.3	10.6 \pm 0.5
- SaO ₂ (%)	-	-	5.8 \pm 2.3	5.5 \pm 1.5	5.5 \pm 1.5	5.4 \pm 0.7
- pH	-	-	6.87 \pm 0.02	6.92 \pm 0.02	6.91 \pm 0.02	6.96 \pm 0.02#
- Base excess (mmol/L)	-	-	-13.9 \pm 1.1	-14.0 \pm 0.6	-13.4 \pm 0.9	-12.5 \pm 1.3
- Lactate (mmol/L)	-	-	9.4 \pm 0.6	7.5 \pm 0.5	8.9 \pm 0.4	7.3 \pm 0.8
Resuscitation						
- Adrenaline use	0% (0/9)	0% (0/6)	25% (4/16)	42% (5/12)	29% (4/14)	33% (2/6)
- Spontaneous breathing (min)	10 \pm 3	53 \pm 28	669 \pm 383*	351 \pm 296	25 \pm 4	59 \pm 16
- Ventilation time (min)	21 \pm 3	72 \pm 34	694 \pm 381*	800 \pm 475	78 \pm 18	101 \pm 21
MAINTENANCE						
Temperature (°C)						
- Time to goal temperature (h)	-	-	-	2.7 \pm 0.6	-	2.2 \pm 0.3
- Time at goal (%)	-	-	-	67 \pm 5	-	74 \pm 8
- 4 h	38.6 \pm 0.2	38.7 \pm 0.1	38.6 \pm 0.1	38.0 \pm 0.3	38.8 \pm 0.3	37.8 \pm 0.7
- 12 h	38.3 \pm 0.4	37.9 \pm 0.2	38.0 \pm 0.3	35.2 \pm 0.1#ϕ	37.7 \pm 0.4	35.9 \pm 0.4#ϕ
- 24 h	38.2 \pm 0.2	39.1 \pm 0.1*	38.5 \pm 0.2	34.9 \pm 0.1#ϕ	38.6 \pm 0.1	35.2 \pm 0.2#ϕ
- 48 h	38.4 \pm 0.3	39.5 \pm 0.1*	38.8 \pm 0.1	38.5 \pm 0.2	38.4 \pm 0.2	38.8 \pm 0.3
- 72 h	38.7 \pm 0.3	39.3 \pm 0.2	39.0 \pm 0.1	39.0 \pm 0.1	38.7 \pm 0.2	39.6 \pm 0.2 ϕ
Heart rate (bpm)						
- 4 h	168 \pm 15	181 \pm 13	184 \pm 8	176 \pm 8	177 \pm 9	201 \pm 9
- 12 h	194 \pm 7	199 \pm 12	165 \pm 10	209 \pm 3#ϕ	149 \pm 9	215 \pm 7#ϕ
- 24 h	189 \pm 10	212 \pm 10	189 \pm 8	190 \pm 4	174 \pm 11	206 \pm 9
- 48 h	204 \pm 17	200 \pm 16	203 \pm 13	185 \pm 8	194 \pm 11	190 \pm 18
- 72 h	203 \pm 1	208 \pm 2	198 \pm 21	188 \pm 9	193 \pm 7	189 \pm 10
Oxygen saturation (%)						
- 4 h	92.0 \pm 1.7	96.5 \pm 1.1	97.1 \pm 0.7*	95.9 \pm 1.0	92.8 \pm 1.7	96.5 \pm 1.5

- 12 h	94.6 ± 1.3	96.2 ± 1.4	96.3 ± 0.8	95.9 ± 0.8	98.1 ± 0.4	97.0 ± 1.3
- 24 h	97.3 ± 0.8	98.5 ± 1.0	98.6 ± 0.4	95.9 ± 0.9	98.3 ± 0.6	98.3 ± 0.6
- 48 h	97.9 ± 0.5	97.0 ± 1.3	98.4 ± 0.4	99.1 ± 0.3	97.8 ± 0.6	98.3 ± 0.6
- 72 h	96.9 ± 0.9	99.4 ± 0.4	97.7 ± 0.6	98.7 ± 0.6	97.1 ± 1.0	99.0 ± 0.5
Base excess (mmol/L)						
- 4 h	-4.8 ± 1.4	-4.9 ± 0.8	-4.3 ± 1.0	-1.9 ± 0.7	-5.1 ± 1.0	-3.4 ± 1.7
- 12 h	-2.5 ± 0.6	-5.0 ± 0.9	-7.9 ± 1.3*	-5.5 ± 0.8	-6.8 ± 1.0	-2.2 ± 2.3
- 24 h	4.0 ± 0.5	0.7 ± 1.3	-0.2 ± 1.2	-1.2 ± 0.5	-2.2 ± 1.4	0.9 ± 1.7
- 48 h	4.6 ± 1.2	3.4 ± 1.0	3.6 ± 1.1	5.6 ± 1.1	6.2 ± 1.0	0.5 ± 5.1
- 72 h	4.3 ± 1.3	3.0 ± 1.2	1.0 ± 2.0	2.1 ± 1.7	2.9 ± 0.9	5.0 ± 0.8
Lactate (mmol/L)						
- 4 h	3.8 ± 0.5	4.6 ± 0.6	5.0 ± 0.5	2.2 ± 0.3#φ	5.5 ± 0.8	2.8 ± 0.4φ
- 12 h	4.7 ± 0.5	4.9 ± 0.7	8.7 ± 0.9*	6.0 ± 0.8	8.0 ± 0.8	3.8 ± 0.4#φ
- 24 h	3.0 ± 0.2	3.8 ± 0.3	4.6 ± 0.5*	3.6 ± 0.4φ	5.9 ± 0.8	2.5 ± 0.4φ
- 48 h	2.3 ± 0.2	3.7 ± 0.4	2.4 ± 0.2	2.3 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.3	1.6 ± 0.3
- 72 h	2.0 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.3	3.1 ± 0.8	2.2 ± 0.3	1.8 ± 0.3

Table 2. Lamb functional outcomes. Significantly different values are indicated in bold. Data are mean ± standard error of the mean. *p<0.05 vs control; #p<0.05 vs asphyxia; ^p<0.05 vs asphyxia+TH.

	Control	Control+MLT	Asphyxia	Asphyxia+TH	Asphyxia+MLT	Asphyxia+TH+MLT
FUNCTIONAL OUTCOMES						
Glucose infusion required	33% (3/9)	0% (0/6)	100% (16/16)*	100% (12/12)	71% (10/14)	100% (6/6)
Established formula feeding	100% (9/9)	100% (6/6)	80% (13/16)	75% (9/12)	100% (14/14)^	100% (6/6)
Time of established feeding (h)	2.1 ± 0.8	2.1 ± 0.6	20.5 ± 7.0*	50.4 ± 7.4#	6.4 ± 1.5^	11.1 ± 4.7^
Standing ability at 72 h	100% (9/9)	100% (6/6)	69% (11/16)	25% (3/12)#	93% (13/14)^	100% (6/6)^
Standing attained (h)	4.1 ± 0.9	6.5 ± 1.9	36 ± 6.2*	66.5 ± 2.7#	20.0 ± 5.5^	35.5 ± 5.5^
Seizures present over experiment	0% (0/9)	0% (0/6)	44% (7/16)*	17% (2/12)	7% (1/14)	0% (0/6)
Time asleep over 24 h (%)	37%	63%*	66%*	92%#	84%#	93%#

Fig. 1. Melatonin (MLT) concentration. MLT concentrations in plasma (A) were significantly increased in control+MLT, asphyxia+MLT and asphyxia+TH+MLT over the experimental period. MLT concentration showed a prolonged increase in asphyxia+TH+MLT animals. MLT concentration within the cortex (B) was significantly elevated in all MLT-treated groups. Data are mean \pm standard error of the mean. The results from 2-way ANOVA amongst asphyxia groups are shown on the figure. * $p < 0.05$ vs control; # $p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia; ^ $p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia+TH; $\phi p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia+MLT.

Fig. 2. Magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS). Lactate:Choline (A) was significantly increased in the asphyxia group compared to control. There were no significant differences following 2-way ANOVA among asphyxia groups. NAA:Choline (B) showed a significant deficit in the asphyxia group compared to control, indicating neuronal impairment. 2-way ANOVA within asphyxia groups revealed a significant interaction between TH and MLT ($p=0.03$). Lactate:NAA (C) was increased in the asphyxia group compared to control. 2-way ANOVA within asphyxia groups showed a significant effect with MLT treatment ($p=0.008$). Data presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean. The results from 2-way ANOVA amongst asphyxia groups are shown on the figures. * $p<0.05$ vs control.

Fig. 3. Markers of cerebral oxidative stress. Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration (A) within cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) was significantly increased in asphyxia animals compared to control. 2-way ANOVA across asphyxia groups show that both therapeutic hypothermia (TH) and melatonin (MLT) significantly reduced MDA concentration compared to asphyxia alone. (B) 4-hydroxynonenal (4-HNE; log scale) cell counts from the cortex

(molecular layer), hippocampus (CA1), thalamus (paraventricular nuclei), striatum (external capsule), and subcortical white matter. 4-HNE-positive cells were not significantly different from controls after asphyxia. 2-way ANOVA across asphyxia groups showed that MLT decreased 4-HNE count within the thalamus only and TH did not affect 4-HNE cell counts. Data presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean. The results from 2-way ANOVA amongst asphyxia groups are shown on each panel. * $p < 0.05$ vs control; # $p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia; ^ $p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia+TH.

Fig. 4. Markers of cerebral inflammation. IL-1 β concentration (A) within cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) was significantly increased following asphyxia compared to control. (B) Ionized calcium binding adapter molecule (IBA-1) cell counts within the cortex (molecular layer), hippocampus (CA1), thalamus (paraventricular nuclei), striatum (external capsule), and subcortical white matter. Asphyxia significantly increased IBA-1 cell counts in

all brain regions except the thalamus compared to control. 2-way ANOVA across asphyxia groups showed that TH reduced IBA-1 cell counts within all brain regions except the white matter and MLT reduced counts in all regions except the striatum. Data presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean. The results from 2-way ANOVA amongst asphyxia groups are shown on the figures. * $p < 0.05$ vs control; # $p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia.

Fig. 5. Markers of cerebral cell death. S100B concentration (A) within the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) was significantly increased in asphyxia-only animals compared to control. Across asphyxia groups, MLT treatment was associated with a decrease in CSF S100B, but TH was not. (B) Neurons stained with cresyl violet-acid fuchsin and demonstrating evidence of cellular necrosis were counted and (C) activated caspase-3 % area staining for apoptosis within the cortex (molecular layer), hippocampus (CA1), thalamus (paraventricular nuclei), striatum (external capsule), and subcortical white matter. Asphyxia was associated with a significant increase in cellular necrosis and apoptosis in all brain regions compared to control. 2-way ANOVA across asphyxia groups showed that TH reduced neuronal necrosis within the hippocampus, thalamus and striatum and reduced apoptosis across all regions, while MLT reduced both necrosis and apoptosis in all brain regions. Data are mean \pm standard error of the mean. The results from 2-way ANOVA amongst asphyxia groups are presented on the figure. * $p < 0.05$ vs control; # $p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia; ^ $p < 0.05$ vs asphyxia+TH.

Fig. 6. Photomicrographs from brain tissue collected at 72 h after birth. Representative images are from the striatum (external capsule) for staining with 4-hydroxynonenal (4-HNE; **A-E**), ionized calcium binding adapter molecule (IBA-1; **F-J**), cresyl violet-acid fuchsin (CVAF; **K-O**) and activated caspase-3 (Cas-3; **P-T**). White arrows indicate cells showing evidence of necrosis; scale bar = 100 μ m.